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LIFE ON THE FAULTLINES OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: CRITICAL GAPS AND CREATIVE CO-EVOLUTION

How to escape Artificial Intelligence's obviousness in order to open virtuous possibilities?

AI's disruption is not only technical: it is most importantly the demand that we rethink ourselves, our choices, and the society we want to build.

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) unsettles us not only by what it does, but by how it is handed to us: as a monolithic proposition, with little room for alternative paths. This raises unsettling questions. What if the way AI is offered to us is itself the trap? Can machines truly serve society, or only standardize it? How do we let AI expand us, instead of reducing or excluding us?

These are not technical puzzles but existential ones. AI compels us to step back, to rethink our frameworks, and to decide whether it will confine us. Or help us reinvent who we are.

Artificial intelligence as object and lever of de-coincidence

AI is shaking our reference points at dizzying speed. Faced with a technology that fascinates us as much as it destabilizes us by widening the gap with our familiar frames of meaning, we often oscillate between incomprehension and apprehension, between wonder and outright rejection.

These reactions, while understandable, trap us in a binary logic that risks making us miss what matters most: beyond the collective value it may bring, AI perhaps offers us a historic opportunity to fundamentally rethink our relationship to the world and to ourselves. Instead of giving in to the illusion of techno-solutionism, which claims that every problem can be solved by the sheer power of algorithms, we might each, in an active posture, explore its uses deliberately so that technology becomes a fertile lever for reinventing our frameworks of thought and action.

While authors such as Rob Reich (*System Error*, 2021) or Mustafa Suleyman (*The Coming Wave*, 2023) analyze AI's systemic impacts (on democracy, the economy, regulation), few have asked how it influences our mental frameworks and our relationship to ourselves. It is precisely here that François Jullien's philosophy opens an original perspective: instead of locking us into a binary choice between categorical rejection and blind adoption, it proposes a conscious practice of *de-coïncidence*. This creative act of generating a fruitful gap with normative "obviousness"

enables us to break away from automatic adhesion to dominant frameworks and to open up new spaces of thought and action. Applied to AI, this approach does not stop at critique or regulation: it allows us to reinvest in the technology actively, to fracture dominant narratives so that other possibilities may emerge. As François Jullien reminds us, citing Solzhenitsyn: “*Caves begin to collapse through cracks.*”

This original approach opens four useful avenues:

1. Freeing ourselves from the monolithic vision of AI as presented by its designers.
2. Transforming our intimate relationship to what AI produces, making it a tool of emancipation rather than subordination.
3. Using it as a revealer of rigidities (“coincidences,” in Jullien’s terms): collective adhesions where ideas or systems impose themselves as normative “truths,” neutralizing all contestation and enclosing us, whether at the societal level (external) or personal level (intimate).
4. Exploring nascent cognitive symbiosis, by conceiving of AI as a new alterity with which we can enter into co-evolution.

Rethinking the AI revolution beyond its li-myths

AI beyond the imaginaries: definitions and realities

The term *artificial intelligence* functions as a powerful trigger for imaginaries and semantic projections. It ties a complex, symbolically charged human notion (*intelligence*) to a technological qualifier (*artificial*). Together they evoke anthropomorphic imitation, functional reproduction, and a sense of strangeness or distance.

This opens up a wide interpretive space, fueled by countless cultural references (notably science fiction), by media narratives that are often simplistic or sensationalist, and by a lack of understanding of technical foundations. These projected fantasies reflect both our aspirations and our fears in the face of a possible replication (or surpassing) of human capacities. They affect not only how each person understands what AI

really is, and how public opinion is shaped in spite of this, but also the framing of ethical debates, research priorities, and public policies designed to regulate AI's development. Such confusions and misunderstandings make precise communication and broad education on the subject all the more urgent.

Given the pace of its expansion, a fresh, accurate definition of AI is necessary. It is tempting to reduce it to predictive technology or decision-support systems serving predefined goals. Yet in reality, AI covers a wide range of systems and approaches: from conversational agents to creative algorithms, from autonomous vehicles to "weak AI" and the still-speculative "strong AI."

A definition of AI suited to our discussion could be:

"AI is a scientific and technological field that seeks to enable machines to perform tasks traditionally associated with human intelligence, such as learning, logical reasoning, perception, planning, and creativity."

This field rests on two main technological approaches:

- Statistical machine-learning algorithms trained on large volumes of data, and
- So-called "symbolic" algorithms that solve problems through explicitly defined rules.

The combination of the two makes it possible to design systems that are both adaptive and explainable to learn from data while integrating logical rules to better structure decision-making.

Even before the rise of generative AI, uses already ranged from medical and financial analysis to artistic creation and deepfakes. AI is penetrating every aspect of our lives and, in doing so, raising specific ethical, social, and political issues. It cannot be reduced to a mere technical advance: in its current form, it embodies a particular conception of humanity and society. Public forums, for example, could be convened to explore how recommendation algorithms shape cultural choices and worldviews by favoring certain norms at the expense of diversity.

Depending on how it is defined and used, AI can trace very different pathways for our lives. While it simulates (and sometimes seems to surpass) certain human cognitive abilities, it also opens up a space of creation and exploration, far beyond the binary opposition of human versus machine. It offers the opportunity to reinvent our relationship with ourselves and with the world, instead of locking us into a narrow vision of intelligence and its future.

From coal to data: the new extractivist model

To think clearly about our relationship with AI, we must also understand the dynamics of its development and diffusion. Today, its advancement is driven by a complementary ecosystem: researchers in public and private labs, teams within large organizations, specialized startups, open-source communities, and many others. Its diffusion, however, is largely controlled by the platforms of digital giants, which set the terms of access and usage. AI is now everywhere, in companies and in society.

The deployment of generative AI at the end of 2022 marks a historic turning point. Whereas the computerization of the 1980s–1990s or the digital transition of the 2000s–2010s followed a hierarchical logic, where adoption was driven and controlled by organizations, generative AI is spreading through the opposite dynamic: bottom-up. Individuals appropriate these tools on their own initiative, outside established institutional structures. This phenomenon of *shadow AI* creates a new tension between individual initiative and organizational strategy, forcing institutions to urgently rethink their modes of technological governance and raising challenges of culture, training, and adaptation.

The spread of AI signals the start of a new industrial revolution, this time not mechanical, but cognitive, transforming our relationship to knowledge and decision-making. Whereas earlier industrial shifts automated material production, the AI revolution targets cognitive processes. The logic of rationalization and productivity gains remains, but with a crucial difference: the raw material is now data, the traces of our lives and societies, continuously captured by AI. “Data is the new gold,” as the now-standard phrase goes.

The rise of modern AI reveals a geography of power that is as fascinating as it is troubling. Philosopher Shannon Vallor describes this concentration of technological power as AI's true danger: it encodes the biases and attitudes of a narrow circle of designers, reinforcing a reductive vision of humanity and the world. This concentration reflects more than economic or technical asymmetry: it crystallizes a particular worldview, emerging from a homogeneous ecosystem shaped by gender dominance, specialized training, imperatives of profitability, and narrow conceptions of intelligence, the common good, and progress. This cultural uniformity seeps into the very DNA of AI systems, a form of invisible cultural code guiding their development.

Several recent developments suggest the early seeds of a welcome productive misalignment in advanced AI systems. The massive investments previously required to develop these systems now seem increasingly hard to justify. The effectiveness of the *Bigger is Better* approach in large language models (LLMs) and large reasoning models (LRMs) is contested: some researchers predict exponential gains in capability as models scale, while others, like Yann LeCun, consider this path a technological dead end: fertile in applications, perhaps, but sterile in advancing AI's real cognitive capacities.

Growing centralization also risks distorting the relationship between technology and society: the increasing opacity of systems, the capture of personal data, and the enormous ecological footprint of the infrastructures required together sketch a development model that seems to reproduce, if not amplify, the very asymmetries it claimed it would solve.

The advent of generative AI illustrates the scale of this reconfiguration of power. Through the mobilization of unprecedented financial and computational resources, it inaugurates a new technological race that erases the traditional boundaries between industrial innovation and geopolitical power.

This shift marks less a rupture than an evolution of capitalism. By substituting a logic of accumulation through control and extraction for the classical mechanisms of competition and production, digital platforms reinvent medieval structures in the digital age. As Cédric Durand argues in

Techno-féodalisme: Critique de l'économie numérique (2020), they establish dominance over essential infrastructures, capture the value created by users, and weave dependency networks through systematic rent extraction. This new architecture of power undermines traditional frameworks of regulation and sovereignty and creates strong “coincidences” (constraints from which it is difficult, if not impossible, to deviate) forcing us to question fundamentally how these systems are governed.

And with the extractivist model of AI, founded on massive data capture and opaque exploitation, there arises, beyond the risks to privacy and individual autonomy, the danger of collective dispossession: a loss of informational sovereignty, of our capacity to shape our own narratives and decisions, and more broadly, of our control over the conditions of knowledge production and interpretation. This dispossession calls for new approaches: not to extract ever more data, but to make smarter and more ethical use of it.

The fundamental paradox of a technology meant to democratize knowledge that instead concentrates power invites us to rethink the conditions for a truly emancipatory AI.

The recent boom of generative AI also raises urgent questions about its environmental footprint. Its carbon impact, both in training and in use, is troubling and calls into question the sustainability of its growth in a resource-limited world. Technological breakthroughs such as the one announced by China's DeepSeek, which drastically reduces both the financial and environmental costs of model training, may look promising.

Yet, as Satya Nadella warns:

“Jevons’ paradox strikes again. As AI becomes more efficient and accessible, its use will explode, turning it into a commodity we simply cannot do without.”

The stakes go beyond technical innovation: they force us to reconsider our relationship to technology at the intersection of collective progress, social justice, and energy sobriety.

Between promises and illusions: limits and horizons of AI

The possible trajectories of AI have become the subject of numerous foresight studies, which sketch out divergent paths. The debate about the advent of artificial general intelligence (AGI), a form of AI able to autonomously adapt to novel contexts and rival human intelligence across a wide range of tasks, reveals less a scientific consensus than a field of tension between competing visions of technological development.

The dizzying prospect of a super-AI that surpasses human capacities in every domain and escapes all control agitates both media and research circles, and fuels a large body of literature. For some, this is science fiction; for others, it is a very real existential risk. Either way, it raises thorny questions about the long-term governance of AI and the degree of societal involvement required in shaping its development.

The traditional dichotomy between *weak* and *strong* AI is being complicated today by the emergence of large language and reasoning models, and by advances in new architectures such as mixture-of-experts (MoE) models or autonomous agents able to plan and execute complex tasks. These innovations open perspectives for advanced automation across many domains. They blur established boundaries by displaying remarkable capabilities while simultaneously revealing fundamental limitations. These systems excel at manipulating symbols and generating content, but without the deep understanding that characterizes human intelligence. They thus embody an in-between state that challenges our conceptual frameworks.

However, these systems also carry within them an intrinsic tendency toward *bullshit*¹ (formerly known as *hallucinations*) which as a team of mathematicians recently demonstrated, is structurally built into the models. This tendency amplifies errors and prejudices at scale, raising critical questions of ethical alignment and governance.

This technical evolution does not follow a deterministic trajectory, despite the narratives advanced by dominant actors in the field. AI is not

¹ The AI research community is increasingly moving away from the misleading term “hallucination” to adopt *bullshit*, in Harry Frankfurt’s sense: producing statements that are convincing without regard for their truthfulness.

“coincident” by nature; rather, it is the *proposals* being made to us that are coincident. It is precisely here that François Jullien’s thought proves valuable: not as a ready-made solution, but as a method for navigating the uncharted waters of transforming the destabilization caused by AI into an opportunity for reinvention.

Cracking and reinventing: de-coïncidence according to François Jullien

The tension between technological determinism and collective deliberation calls for a structured response: why don’t academic institutions, citizen groups, and technology companies collaborate more, right now, to design an open approach to AI? Such collaboration would allow for a collective reappropriation not by attempting to overthrow massive systems head-on or limiting ourselves to abstract denunciations, but by working in the margins, in a modest yet profoundly effective way: through the cracks.

By nature discreet and often imperceptible, a crack possesses a force of continuous and irreversible erosion. It is neither spectacular nor immediately radical, but it is precisely this subtlety that makes it effective. By working its way into structures, it quietly weakens certainties, balances, and apparent convergences, eventually causing reconfigurations and sometimes collapse. History is full of examples of seemingly unshakable systems that disintegrated under the pressure of ideological, social, or cultural fissures. The Berlin Wall, for instance, fell less from one single act of destruction than from the accumulation of invisible tensions, ideological fractures, and successive micro-resistances.

The crack is not an accident; it is a process. This is where François Jullien’s concept of *de-coïncidence* demonstrates its full potential: by identifying the interstices and latent tensions within experiential frameworks and established systems, it brings to light those tipping points that dominant logics tend to ignore. It destabilizes consensus by pointing to phenomena held to be convergent or harmonious that actually conceal internal contradictions, in reality fertile points of tension. By making them

visible, it opens a space for transformation not through direct opposition, but through the subtle displacement of frames of thought and action.

The strength of this approach lies in the fact that the crack is effective from the start. By naming gaps, it already begins to widen them by shifting perspectives; it acts upon structures. Far from being a mere injunction, it does not stop at exposing tensions but operates in the active sense of the word, recharging situations with new possibilities. It offers a method of intervention, both analytical and transformative, to generate alternatives where uniformity previously seemed to reign.

Where Jacques Derrida revealed the instability of concepts, Bernard Stiegler analyzed the structuring impact of technology, and Bruno Latour mapped sociotechnical entanglements, François Jullien opens a new operational path: by identifying and amplifying AI's fertile ruptures, we move beyond denouncing the external threat of algorithmic control, and instead reveal subtle spaces where autonomy and invention can take root. These, in turn, become levers for reinvesting technology differently.

De-coinciding in practice: an ethics of reappropriation

De-coïncidence asserts itself on three fronts: existential, by redefining our humanity in the face of the machine; ethical, by ensuring an AI that is compatible with our values and respectful of our diversities, as Cédric Villani puts it; and political, through the need to mobilize science, the arts, law, and civil society in a collective effort.

Toward a transformative *praxis*

Concretely, in order to make this philosophical reflection operative, each of us must find our own ways of broadening our frameworks of experience, of turning confrontation into an opportunity for creativity. The practice of de-coïncidence cannot be reduced to a universal methodology: it must also be embodied in a transformative *praxis*, one that operates simultaneously on the individual and collective levels, and that unfolds along complementary dimensions, each requiring its own specific learning.

The first is attentiveness to gaps: it means learning to recognize, in our daily interactions with AI, those moments when the unexpected emerges, when a breach opens in the apparent determinism of systems. These instants, whether it is a surprising response from a conversational agent or an unforeseen creation by a generative AI, become invitations to think differently.

The second is creative experimentation: once such fissures appear, how do we seize them, broaden them, turn them into spaces of innovation? This requires abandoning both the posture of a simple user and that of a detached critic. What is called for is an exploratory practice of AI, where each interaction becomes a chance to experiment, to divert, to reinvent prescribed uses.

And if learning this practice begins at the individual level, it can only develop fully in a collective setting. This means rethinking our institutions, our pedagogical methods, our modes of public deliberation, so that they integrate this dimension of creative displacement, even within the constrained context of the coincident proposals presented to us by AI developers.

De-coinciding from a monolithic AI

A first task would be to de-coincide from the model imposed by AI's designers: a monolithic, top-down approach, offered without real consultation of the public it concerns, and as such eminently coincident.

Large language models, for example, are trained on massive datasets drawn from the raw material of the web, digitized libraries, and corpora such as Wikipedia. Yet these data are shot through with pre-existing social and cultural biases. As a result, the productions of generative AI systems often reproduce and sometimes amplify these biases. When such systems become widely used, the phenomenon leads to an invisible normalization of these biases. Becoming aware of this effect is crucial, both to extract ourselves from it and to protect ourselves against it.

These new convergences gradually shape our representations of what is possible, homogenizing our frameworks of interaction with AI. The result is a technology that, while seemingly broad in scope, is opaque in its

functioning and ultimately rigid in its prescribed uses, leaving little space for creative appropriation by users.

Faced with this systemic coincidence where, under the guise of performance and efficiency, AI subtly normalizes our modes of thought and action, concealing its ideological weight behind a veneer of technical neutrality, the practice of de-coïncidence calls for integrating plural perspectives into the very design of systems. To this end, open governance, based on mechanisms of collective self-regulation and greater transparency, seems essential. The open-source approach, by combining technical innovation with distributed governance, is one way to fracture this imposed standardization.

Inherited from the free-software movement, open source offers a tangible alternative to the concentration of technical infrastructures. Yet its implementation is complex: unlike traditional software, AI models involve the opening of three technical components: architecture, weights, and training data. The tension between openness and hardware capacity represents a major challenge for the financing of open-source AI. Confronted with the massive investments of private actors that drive ultra-rapid innovation, open source struggles to keep pace.

To address this asymmetry, the creation of a European fund dedicated to open-source AI, modeled on the European Innovation Fund, would make it possible to mobilize resources commensurate with the stakes, combining public financing, regulated private investment, and targeted philanthropic contributions. We might also imagine cooperative data models, where users finance and control AI infrastructures, supporting open innovation in the manner of crowdfunding initiatives that have sustained free software.

The issue goes beyond technique: it is profoundly political. Only an AI under open governance will allow us to escape dominant models and reclaim control over our digital future.

Freeing the use of AI: moving beyond imposed coincidences

A second challenge is to de-coincide from the many implicit alignments generated by the massive adoption of AI systems. This means questioning their uses and their outputs, diverting them if necessary, and turning them into levers for transformation not by rejecting or passively enduring them, but by learning to master them, to inhabit the space between human and machine where tensions and potentialities reveal themselves.

AI alters our frameworks of thought by confronting us with other forms of reasoning. By contrast, it highlights our own capacities for contextualization and creativity, drawing attention to the specificities of human intelligence and fostering a reflexivity that is essential to intellectual autonomy. It pushes us to move beyond the traditional vision of creativity as pure invention *ex nihilo*. Generative AI makes evident that innovation often arises from recomposition, from the crossing and repurposing of existing elements.

And unlike the human being, who is capable of standing outside the world he inhabits (“*ex-isting*”), AI is intrinsically bound to the closed universe of its design and training parameters. Recommendation algorithms tend to confine users within cognitive bubbles: someone inclined to conspiracy videos on YouTube will see their feed saturated with similar content, reinforcing a biased vision of the world. On Spotify, a generated playlist reduces exposure to less popular styles, impoverishing musical diversity. The examples are numerous. Once made visible (and therefore contestable) the coincidences in how these systems produce outcomes open up the possibility of exploring alternative paths: philosophically (how does AI reshape our understanding of thought, creativity, and decision-making?), epistemologically (what new paradigms of knowledge and communication emerge from this technological symbiosis?), and pragmatically (how can we cultivate a fertile interaction with these systems while preserving our fundamental autonomy?).

De-coinciding from these systems requires an active cultivation of diversity in uses. Encouraging this diversity means funding alternative AI projects explicitly, for example, through dedicated incubators or by integrating into

public tenders criteria that emphasize diversity of approaches and interoperability. It also means creating libraries of alternative interactions within user interfaces (systematically offering multiple possible formulations), establishing open interoperability protocols between competing AI systems, or developing multi-criteria evaluation frameworks that explicitly value divergent approaches. Users themselves must be equipped to configure, divert, and even contribute actively to the systems they employ.

The goal is to make AI, beyond open source, into an appropriable digital commons, rather than a proprietary infrastructure imposed upon us. By fostering experimentation, adaptability, and co-construction, it becomes possible to escape imposed trajectories and to broaden the horizon of possibilities. Several practical avenues could be explored immediately. Chief among them, to train individuals in critical thinking and teach them how to adjust the outputs of these technologies, educational institutions could:

- develop pedagogical tools reaching the broadest possible audience, such as short AI modules in middle- and high-school curricula, emphasizing hands-on experimentation rather than theory;
- set up online platforms that allow students and citizens to visualize and manipulate model biases in concrete cases;
- organize regular community workshops on prompt engineering, where citizens and developers collaborate to explore system limitations.

Reinforcing interoperability among AI systems would also allow users to combine the outputs of multiple models, creating a richer and more varied space of use. Comparative interfaces, displaying side by side the analyses or productions from different AI models, could be developed. The creation of open experimental environments already offers opportunities to test interoperable systems in critical contexts such as health or education, and to demonstrate their effectiveness. Finally, designing AI systems capable of recognizing and signaling their own limitations would be essential to ensuring responsible and transparent use. Such self-assessment mechanisms would allow systems to indicate zones of uncertainty or

potential bias in their analyses, strengthening user trust while reducing the risk of misinterpretation.

De-coinciding from the production of AI systems is thus an imperative of cognitive and collective sovereignty, in order to guarantee an AI that serves emancipation rather than standardization.

AI as operator of de-coïncidence

Finally, why not mobilize AI itself to identify and overcome the imposed and problematic convergences that structure our daily lives?

Because of its exceptional capacity to analyze vast quantities of data and detect subtle patterns, AI can help us fracture rigid frameworks. Properly used, it becomes a powerful tool of critical analysis, an extrinsic operator of de-coïncidence, capable of revealing the invisible mechanisms that trap our societies in repetitive and constraining patterns, and of highlighting opportunities for improvement and unexplored alternatives.

In 2023, for example, a team of researchers from Berkeley and Stanford used AI to analyze a large number of judicial decisions, exposing systemic discrimination and disparities in the American judicial system. By bringing to light long-invisible patterns, AI supported a more equitable justice system while enriching collective reflection on judicial practices. It became an instrument of critical distance, able to illuminate blind spots in the system and catalyze positive transformation.

AI could likewise be used to detect bias in recruitment processes, inequalities in hiring policies, or weaknesses in supply chains.

Studies, including those conducted at the MIT Media Lab, have employed AI to analyze interactions on social networks. They showed how recommendation algorithms can foster political polarization and the formation of informational bubbles, limiting exposure to diverse perspectives and deepening ideological divides. These analyses revealed a gap between the ideal of an open public debate and the fragmented reality of online exchanges.

Governments must quickly use AI to explore alternative decisions by simulating the impact of new policies, because one of AI's major contributions is its ability to highlight externalities, those side effects that are often ignored in economic, industrial, or social decisions. Too often obscured by standardized indicators or dominant interests, these externalities (environmental repercussions, impacts on local communities, institutional fragmentation of responsibilities) remain outside the scope of political decision-making. By making them visible and understandable, AI could expand the horizons of governance and integrate a systemic perspective, grounded in a more comprehensive analysis of long-term consequences.

But for AI to fully play this role, mechanisms must be created that are open to questioning and to collective experimentation. This could involve three complementary measures: algorithmic deliberation interfaces, where results are accompanied by alternatives generated with different parameters; citizen observatories equipped with accessible technical audit tools; and development processes that systematically include adversarial testing phases, in which diverse collectives seek to identify the system's blind spots. In this way, a contestable AI could emerge, one designed to be questioned, revised, and repurposed by the communities concerned, rather than to impose opaque and irrevocable decisions.

The dominance of *single thought* ("*pensée unique*" in French) locks debate, marginalizes alternatives, and reinforces dominant narratives. This is what François Jullien denounces when he writes:

"To debate, to stand up against single thought is in fact the most coincident theme of all, for it remains comfortably within established thought and only ruffles its surface while giving the flattering illusion of criticizing it."

This observation resonates strongly in the context of AI. It suggests that AI could help move beyond single thought by mapping the diversity of opinions and making visible the blind spots of public debate. To achieve this, however, it must be supported by rigorous data collection and structuring, drawing on varied sources: traditional media, social platforms, blogs, citizen forums. The goal is to avoid AI itself becoming an agent of

reinforcement for dominant narratives. This requires strict and transparent governance. The issue is not to replace one bias with another, but to provide access to broader perspectives and to prevent the tool from serving the interests of the most powerful actors. If well designed and responsibly used, AI can revitalize public debate by exposing citizens to a diversity of viewpoints and by facilitating the emergence of consensus based on objectified realities. By valuing disruptive ideas and revealing connections between opposing perspectives, it can also help reduce ideological divisions.

Far from being only an amplifier of existing systems, AI, conceived as an instrument of de-coincidence, can stimulate bold reforms and guide more enlightened decisions, offering an alternative to rigid frameworks and a means of expanding the field of the possible in the service of a more conscious and resilient collective progress.

Dancing with AI: toward co-evolution?

In the introduction to his book *Co-intelligence* (2024), Ethan Mollick writes:

“After a few hours spent using generative AI systems, (...) you suddenly realize that you are interacting with something new, something foreign, and that things are about to change.”

Generative AI has, for the first time in the history of digital technologies, undeniably passed the Turing test. It reveals a new tension: by blurring the boundary between human dialogue and machine interaction, it raises not just a technical puzzle, but also shakes our deepest certainties about the nature of consciousness and communication. It confronts us with a troubling alterity: what we cannot integrate into our frame of experience is often perceived as monstrous, an incomprehensible difference, a source of fear or rejection. This perception reflects our own limits more than those of technology. Far from being a monster, AI is more accurately an *unheard-of* (*inouï*): it illuminates our blind spots, disrupts our frameworks, and invites us to transcend them. Its otherness calls us to an inner shift. But what, exactly, is this “other” we perceive in modern AI? And what will it change in our relationship to ourselves and to our capacities?

To explore our relation to this alterity of AI, the Nietzschean metaphor of dance proves fruitful. As Frédéric Pouillaude notes: “*Nietzsche says nothing about dance. But he manages to say a lot through it.*”

Just as Nietzsche used dance to express the inexpressible, we can use this image to think about the subtle interplay of mastery and surprise that now characterizes our interaction with AI. For Nietzsche, dance was the highest expression of life-affirmation: the ability to transmute heaviness into lightness, to turn constraint itself into a creative impulse. Today, that intuition sheds new light on the stakes of our coexistence with AI systems. We must now learn to interact with these technologies consciously and creatively, transforming each interaction into an active exploration, in a choreography where critical distance and creative appropriation intertwine, between algorithmic predictability and creative emergence, between mastery and surprise.

The lightness of this dance is not superficial: it is a subtle art of navigating between gaps, of inhabiting tensions productively rather than seeking to resolve them. Nietzsche’s injunction to “dance high” finds here its full resonance: to elevate our relationship with AI into a dynamic form of engagement that transforms constraints into creative opportunities. What emerges is a form of relational ecology, where the tension between the artificial and the human becomes the motor of our shared evolution.

When AI shakes our certainties

The *unheard-of* (*inouï*), as François Jullien defines it, is the irruption of something radically new that eludes our established categories. It resists immediate assimilation, overflows our usual interpretive frameworks. It is literally what has never yet been heard (“*in-oui*”), and in that very sense destabilizes our structures of understanding.

The emergence of AI today manifests this unheard-of with unusual intensity. AI does not merely challenge our knowledge; it shakes the very structure of our relationship to knowledge and to creation. Its ability to generate outputs that exceed our expectations stems from its algorithmic otherness which, while drawing on human patterns of thought, recombines them according to combinatorial logics so foreign to us that they appear

strange. A transitional space opens where our certainties falter, where the familiar becomes unfamiliar, producing the unsettling feeling that what once seemed known has transformed into disconcerting alterity.

In September 2022, Jason Allen won a major art prize with his work *Théâtre d'Opéra Spatial*, created entirely with Midjourney. The event sparked intense debate on the very nature of artistic creation, questioning the boundary between human author and algorithmic tool, and challenging traditional conceptions of originality and innovation.

This confrontation with the unthought-of of technological origin places us before a choice. The temptation is great to domesticate this strangeness, to fold it back into our habitual frameworks, to reduce it to the already-known. Or else, to accept its invitation to deeper transformation. The real challenge is to learn to inhabit this zone of productive discomfort, where the *unheard-of*, precisely because it resists our categories, urges us to rethink them.

Navigating the incommensurable to rethink our relationship to AI

When reflecting on AI's impact on our relationship to the world and to ourselves, one of François Jullien's notions becomes essential. "*There is incommensurable*" in every attempt to grasp reality, he tells us: an irreducible fault line, a resistance to rational framing that, far from being an obstacle, becomes a source of transformation.

Like the number π , infinite yet inscribed in the continuity of the reals, the incommensurable inhabits the very heart of our systems of measurement and understanding, fissuring our apparent mastery of the calculable. Today, AI embodies this tension in a new way.

AI acts as a distorting mirror of our intelligence. On the one hand, it amplifies certain cognitive capacities with unprecedented computational power. On the other hand, it produces results that escape our established categories, forcing us to revisit our most fundamental conceptual frameworks. Without a critical gaze, we run the paradoxical risk of

devaluing precisely those human faculties that AI cannot reproduce, namely contextual intuition and embodied consciousness.

This algorithmic alterity operates at a deeper level than a mere tool or conventional symbolic system. By its very nature, it introduces ruptures that expose and interrogate our assumptions. When a language model offers an unexpected response, or when a generative system produces an artwork that defies our aesthetic conventions, this is not a simple anomaly but the opening of a new space between human intention and computational emergence.

De-coincidence offers a precious method for navigating these unexplored territories. It invites us to consciously inhabit this intermediate space where our certainties falter, where algorithmic strangeness becomes a source of renewal. It asks us to explore the path of a fertile co-evolution, where the incommensurable is no longer a hurdle to be overcome but a catalyst that pushes us to reinvent our modes of thought and creation.

AI as mirror and vector of inner de-coincidence

By overturning our established certainties, AI reveals not only our blind spots but also opens unexplored horizons. It acts as a powerful revealer of what escapes our habitual frameworks, a cognitive mirror that exposes our own biases and limits.

This inner mutation is a profound transformation of our relationship to thought and to ourselves. Confronted with a non-human intelligence that surprises us, compels us to reevaluate our automatisms, and obliges us to reformulate our interpretive frameworks, we are led to redefine both our modes of thinking and our cognitive identity.

This process evokes Jung's concept of individuation, in which the subject, faced with his shadow zones and reflections, gradually frees himself from collective conditionings in order to develop an authentic singularity. AI plays an analogous role in our contemporary cognitive evolution. By confronting us with an artificial alterity whose modes of reasoning are radically different, it invites us to question our unconscious biases and challenge our most entrenched certainties. This confrontation opens the

possibility of a new articulation between our intelligence and cognitive systems that operate according to distinct algorithmic principles.

By enabling us to turn technological alterity into an opportunity for growth, by intensifying our confrontation with the limits of our thinking, AI can become a lever for the emergence of a broader and more integrative consciousness. It invites us to a lucid practice of the tensions between ourselves and the machine, where interaction becomes a source of autonomy and responsibility. This confrontation opens pathways toward a new intellectual autonomy: faced with what AI reveals that cannot be understood within our habitual frameworks, we embark on a process of technological individuation. A trajectory where, rather than adapting passively, we emerge enriched by our encounter with artificial alterity.

Toward cognitive symbiosis

The paradigm of symbiosis, originally from biology, provides a fertile framework for thinking about our relationship with AI. In living systems, symbiosis designates the close and lasting association of different organisms, generating new forms of vitality. Borrowed here, the notion allows us to imagine an analogous relationship at the cognitive level: AI would no longer be merely a tool or an external threat, but a partner in a process of co-evolution.

The biological concept of the holobiont (the organism thought of together with all its symbionts) offers a powerful analogy. Just as coral or the human body function as composite ecosystems, our cognition could be understood as an assemblage that now integrates artificial components. We would thus move from the figure of the isolated individual to that of a cognitive holobiont, where the human is augmented, questioned, and transformed by its interaction with AI.

This transformation cannot be reduced to an increase in performance. It represents a reconfiguration of our very cognitive ecology. Just as gut bacteria influence our health and even our moods, the presence of AI modifies the dynamics of our thinking, revealing blind spots, stimulating imagination, and reshaping our relationship to knowledge.

The risk, however, is that of parasitism rather than symbiosis. Poorly orchestrated, our dependence on AI could lead to the atrophy of critical faculties, to cognitive standardization, or to forms of disempowerment. The challenge is therefore to invent regulatory mechanisms analogous to biological immune systems, capable of maintaining the balance between enrichment and alienation.

Here the method of de-coïncidence shows its full relevance. By keeping open the fissures where otherness asserts itself, it prevents us from being absorbed into technological uniformity. It allows us to cultivate the creative gaps that alone make symbiosis fruitful. For it is not about merging with the machine in a naïve fusion, but about inventing a relational dynamic that enriches both partners.

In this sense, cognitive symbiosis with AI is not a utopian horizon but a process already underway, in need of critical orientation. It requires that we think of ourselves no longer as sovereign subjects facing external tools, but as beings-in-relation, traversed by alterities, and capable of turning them into levers of transformation.

Conclusion: de-coïncidence as a living force

François Jullien's philosophy offers us not only an analytical lens but also a practical method for engaging with the upheavals of our time. Applied to AI, de-coïncidence fissures normative frameworks at both the collective and individual levels, enabling us to resist automatic adhesion and to generate spaces of transformation. It is not an abstract reflection reserved for specialists: it is a living force that must be cultivated in our practices, our institutions, and our modes of governance.

At the collective level, de-coïncidence implies resisting the coincidences imposed by dominant actors. It is a matter of escaping normative narratives by multiplying arenas for interdisciplinary debate and by creating spaces where other perspectives can emerge. The challenge is to prevent technological proposals from hardening into inevitabilities, and instead to preserve the possibility of alternatives. This means refusing to accept the monolithic discourses of large industrial platforms as the only

horizon of progress. It requires creating conditions for genuine plurality: research funded outside the major players, citizen consultation bodies capable of questioning dominant uses, and institutional mechanisms to protect against technological capture.

At the individual level, de-coïncidence requires a vigilant practice of displacement. It invites us to pay attention to those moments when AI unsettles our habits, to transform these disturbances into occasions for creation, and to cultivate an active and lucid relationship with the machine. It is an ethics of reappropriation, where interaction with technology becomes a lever for emancipation rather than for subordination. It asks us not to let ourselves be absorbed by the obviousness of imposed frameworks, but to use each gap, each crack, to reinvent our ways of thinking and acting.

Four concrete directions emerge from this approach.

- The first is to de-coïncide from dominant narratives, by organizing interdisciplinary forums where imposed stories can be fractured and alternatives proposed.
- The second is to de-coïncide from imposed uses, by setting up participatory observatories capable of documenting effects of homogenization and of proposing counter-uses.
- The third is to mobilize AI itself as an operator of de-coïncidence, by designing open and explainable systems that not only identify biases and limits but make them visible to all.
- Finally, the fourth is to use AI as a metacognitive tool: a cognitive symbiont capable of revealing our blind spots, sharpening our reflexivity, and stimulating the reinvention of our frameworks of thought.

The stakes here go beyond technology: they concern the very definition of our humanity. Accepting to be transformed by technique does not mean renouncing our singularity, but reaffirming it differently. It means keeping open the space of reinvention that alone allows us to remain human. For to be human is not to cling to fixed essences, but to inhabit transformation lucidly.

The cracks are already visible. Researchers challenge the dogma of scaling; engineers express unease at the ecological or ethical costs; investors themselves sometimes question the viability of a race that consumes infinite resources. These fissures are not weaknesses to be denied, but precious resources to be cultivated. They are strategic points from which another future can emerge.

To make de-coïncidence a living force is therefore to refuse both naïve enthusiasm and sterile resistance. It is to learn to inhabit tension, to turn destabilization into invention, and to transform each imposed framework into an opportunity for renewal. It means ensuring that AI does not become the instrument of our alienation, but rather the catalyst of our emancipation.

But for this, philosophy must leave the comfort of conceptual abstraction and enter into formats that are accessible and mobilizing. De-coïncidence must become a practical exercise, capable of being shared across cultures and disciplines, disseminated outside academic circles, translated into workshops, narratives, pedagogical tools, and artistic practices. It is by multiplying these concrete mediations that the concept can fully play its role as a force of emancipation.

In this lies perhaps the most precious contribution of de-coïncidence: not to offer ready-made solutions, but to open spaces of possibility. It invites us to accept uncertainty as a condition of freedom, to make cracks not symptoms of fragility but sources of vitality, and to view the upheavals of AI not only as threats to be regulated but also as opportunities to reinvent our relationship to the world.

Ultimately, AI's most precious gift may not be that it makes us more efficient, but that it helps us take a step aside from ourselves. By showing us what escapes us, by revealing our blind spots, by forcing us to re-formulate our frameworks, it reminds us that humanity is not defined once and for all, but is always in the making.

About the author

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